

Mesomorphic Behaviour of Some Esters : Ethyl *p*-(*p*'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)Benzoates

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A new homologous series of mesogenic esters—ethyl *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-benzoates has been synthesized by treating trans-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chlorides with ethyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate and the phase transitions of the various ester mesogens have been determined. Monotropic nematic mesophase is exhibited alternately by the odd members up to the third derivative while the second member exhibits enantiotropic nematic mesophase. The second and third members show smectic mesophase in monotropic conditions. From the fourth member onwards enantiotropic mesomorphism is exhibited. Polymesomorphism begins from the second member though in the monotropic conditions. The nematic-isotropic (even) and smectic-isotropic transition curves, taken in continuation, show a gradual fall followed by a plateau and ending with another smooth fall; the smectic-nematic transition curve shows a steep rise upto the hexyl member. From heptyl to octadecyl derivatives, only smectic mesophase is exhibited with definite transitions to isotropic liquid. While all the nematic phases are with threaded texture, the smectic mesophase shows focal conic Grandjean plates with fan shape texture. The usual odd-even effect is observed not only with regard to nematic mesophase but also the smectic mesophase which is a rare behaviour. Similarities and contrasts with other homologous series yield interesting features. The thermal stabilities are comparable and the mesomorphic range as obtained is quite true to the molecular characteristics. This homologous series of mesogens can be considered to be one of medium melting type though some characteristics of the high melting series are clearly exhibited. In all twelve new mesogens have been investigated for their characteristic behaviour.

L IQUID crystals belong to a class of compounds which are endowed with very specific characteristics of both liquids and crystalline bodies finding a co-existence over a range of temperature and or concentration. Besides academic interest in this specialized class of compounds, there has been sufficient interest aroused on account of their utility in various fields in recent times.

A search for newer and newer mesogens with low melting liquid crystalline properties has begun on a much wider scale due to their increased applications in the field of medicine and electronic display devices. Our present work incorporates synthesis of medium melting new mesogens and study of their characteristics.

Experimental

Synthesis and Study :

A. Preparation of compounds :

1. *p*-*n*-Alkoxybenzaldehydes : These are prepared by the method of Vyas and Shah¹.

2. Trans-*p*-alkoxybenzoic acids : These are prepared from the corresponding *p*-*n*-alkoxybenzaldehydes and malonic acid².

3. Ethyl *p*-hydroxybenzoates : *p*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (50 g) is added to absolute ethanol (200 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2 ml). The mixture is refluxed on water bath for four hours and then poured on ice. The product so obtained is filtered, washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (4*N*) and water. It is crystallized from ethanol (95%) ; yield is 60%, m.p. 116°.

4. Trans-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chlorides : These are prepared from the corresponding acids³.

5. Preparation of esters : Ethyl *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-benzoates are synthesized by treating trans-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chlorides with ethyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate. Dry ethyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate (0.01 mole) is dissolved in dry pyridine (A.R. 10 ml) and added slowly to the trans-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chloride (0.015 mole). The mixture is warmed while shaking for an hour and is allowed to stand overnight. It is acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitates are collected by filtration and are washed with cold dilute sodium bicarbonate solution followed by water. The solid esters are crystallized from ethanol to fine needle-shaped crystals. Yield is approximately 60%. The elemental analysis is in conformity with the calculated values. The transition temperatures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ETHYL *p*-(*p'*-*n*-ALKOXYCINNAMOYLOXY)-BENZOATES

<i>n</i> -Alkyl group	Transition temperature °C		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
Methyl	—	(101.0)	105.0
Ethyl	(83.0)	114.0	120.0
Propyl	(85.5)	(107.0)	122.0
Butyl	95.0	109.0	119.5
Pentyl	100.0	114.5	119.0
Hexyl	88.5	119.5	120.5
Heptyl	80.0	—	118.5
Octyl	89.0	—	121.5
Decyl	72.0	—	123.0
Dodecyl	75.0	—	120.0
Hexadecyl	87.0	—	116.0
Octadecyl	80.0	—	114.5

The values in the parenthesis indicate monotropy.

B. Method of study :

The transitions are studied by (i) the optical method as well as by (ii) using Kofler heating stage polarizing microscope.

Results and Discussion

The structure of the molecules of ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates could be written down as follows :

The molecular structure which is more or less linear with two aromatic rings, one central bridge and sufficiently polar terminal groups at both ends, is quite conducive to exhibition of liquid crystallinity. The molecular geometry will suggest a degree of co-planarity giving almost an ideal length to breadth ratio. 'R' stands for alkyl groups whose chainlength will increase as one proceeds from CH₃ to C₁₈H₃₇.

The homologous series ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates has lower transition temperatures than the corresponding trans-*p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids² which also exhibit mesomorphism due to dimerization of molecules; elimination of dimerization by formation of esters results into a series with lower transitions.

The various characteristic transitions of the homologues are plotted against the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain (Fig. 1). The first and third members are monotropic nematic mesogens while second member exhibits enantiotropic nematic mesophase. Both second and third members exhibit smectic mesophase in monotropic

Fig. 1. Ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxycinnamoyloxy) Benzoates

- Solid Mesomorphic or Solid Isotropic
- △—△ Smectic-Nematic
- Nematic-Isotropic
- Smectic-Isotropic

conditions. The solid-isotropic liquid or solid-mesomorphic curve is shown by dotted line: it rises up to the third member, after which it has a very steep fall up to the fourth member as the series is ascended. Thereafter a zig-zag nature of rise and fall is observed with an overall falling tendency up to the tenth derivative. This is followed by a gradual rise reaching a peak at the hexadecyl member and then a fall up to the end. On account of this the mesomorphic range narrows down and widens up alternatively. Polymesomorphism is exhibited from the fourth homologue since both smectic and nematic mesophases are shown by these members. From the seventh member up to the octadecyl derivative, only smectic mesophase is exhibited as the series is ascended.

There are two nematic-isotropic curves—one that connects the nematic-isotropic transitions having odd number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain and the other that connects the even number of carbon atoms. The usual odd-even effect is observed, i.e. the nematic-isotropic transitions are alternating with odd and even number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain. The reason as advanced⁴

is to be found in the molecular geometry and their orientation in the nematic liquid.

The nematic-isotropic transition temperature curve for the odd members of the alkyl chain show a rising tendency up to the pentyl derivative as the series is ascended. This tendency of rising transition curve has been considered to be a characteristic of low-melting mesogenic homologous series. The transition curve for the even carbon members shows a slight fall followed by an equally slight rise up to decyl homologue after which a smooth fall is observed as the series is ascended.

The two benzene rings contribute towards aromaticity and polarizability of the molecules. The central bridge again enhances the polarizability which increases with increasing length as well as the number of double bonds of the bridge; these give rise to sufficient lateral attractions. The terminal groups with polar nature endow the molecules with terminal attractions which help maintaining an orientation of the molecules. Polar terminal attractions aided by the lateral forces orient the molecules in the fluid state which may be said to be the major factors in the exhibition of a mesophase.

It can be seen that, as far as the present series of mesogens is concerned, the polar nature of the terminal groups is sufficiently pronounced as compared to the forces arising out of the aspects of polarizability; when end to end attractions are more pronounced, the nematic mesophase gets exhibited. When thermal energy is supplied to the molecules as temperature is raised, the molecules in the solid state are capable of resisting it preserving their domain structure intact, but only up to a limit after which, being incapable of resisting the vigorous thermal vibrations as set by the increasing supply of thermal energy, they break down to an isotropic fluid. However, in case of the mesogens, even after the molecules break down to a fluid condition, the terminal and lateral attractions due to the polar nature of the end groups as well as overall polarizability of the molecules, help holding the molecules in a parallel orientation in an end to end or layered manner before they pass into a random redistribution. This kind of parallel orientation of the molecules in the fluid state makes them to exhibit characteristic properties which are mesomorphic in nature. On further supply of energy, the thermal vibrations will increase; a point will reach when the thermal vibrations overcome the resistance offered by the terminal and lateral attractions resulting into an isotropic liquid.

When the terminal attractions are more pronounced, the nematic mesophase will prevail. In this series the first three members show purely nematic mesophase though the second and third members exhibit smectic mesophase on super

cooling. With increase of alkyl chain length as the series is ascended, the overall polarizability will be enhanced. The ratio of terminal attractions to lateral attractions decreases as the series is ascended; the net result is that the lateral attractions gain a predominance over the terminal attractions. The molecules under such conditions will adhere strictly maintaining the layered structure, though partially they might acquire a fluid condition. Under such situation, the layered smectic structure is maintained giving rise to a smectic mesophase. As the temperature is further raised, the strict adherence of the molecules in the layered form gets weakened due to increased thermal vibrations. The molecules will slowly acquire more fluid nature, though they do not abruptly acquire any randomness. At a definite temperature, the layer structure breaks down, but end to end parallel orientation is still maintained giving rise to more fluidity and nematic threaded texture to the molecules. Thus polymesomorphism is exhibited from the second member up to the sixth members of the homologous series.

From the seventh members onwards, purely smectic mesophase is exhibited. The overall polarizability of the molecules gets enhanced as the chainlength of the alkyl chain at one end increases contributing to the exhibition of smectic texture. However, the ratio of terminal to lateral attractions is so low that at a certain stage the thermal vibrations break down the orientation of molecules without giving them a chance for adopting a nematic orientation. Thus only smectic mesophase prevails after the seventh member.

Polymesomorphism is exhibited from the second member up to the sixth homologue. The smectic-nematic transition curves show a steep rise; there are two of them showing alternation effect. Usually an assumption is made that the alkyl chain adopts a zig-zag conformation⁶ with the major axis of the chain statistically normal to the smectic planes. Thus each methylene unit will increase by the same amount the lateral intermolecular attractions on which smectic thermal stability predominantly depends. Therefore S-N temperatures should not alternate. However, the present homologous series deviates remarkably in this regard and while alternation in smectic-nematic transitions is not an usual phenomenon, the homologues of ethyl *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates series exhibit alternation effect even for the smectic-nematic transitions, beginning from the second member up to the hexyl homologue. Though this behaviour is rare and remarkable, it has been observed earlier also in case of the homologous series of *n*-alkyl 4-*p*-methylbenzylideneamino- and 4-*p*-acetoxybenzylidene amino cinnamates⁶. Yet there is a vital difference between these two homologous series. In case of *n*-alkyl 4-*p*-acetoxybenzylideneaminocinnamates, the smectic-nematic transition

curves show a falling tendency while these in case of the present homologous series ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates show a steep rising tendency.

A comparative statement of their thermal stabilities is given in Table 2; it can be seen that the smectic-nematic thermal stability for the present

TABLE 2 RELATIVE SMECTIC-NEMATIC THERMAL STABILITIES

Average transition temperature °C	Ethyl <i>p</i> -(<i>p'</i> - <i>n</i> -alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates	<i>n</i> -alkyl 4- <i>p</i> -acetoxybenzylideneaminocinnamates ⁶
even C ₂ -C ₆	103.8	112.0
odd C ₃ -C ₅	100.0	109.5

homologous series is less than that of the homologous series *n*-alkyl 4-*p*-acetoxybenzylideneaminocinnamates. Obviously there are two benzene rings in both the series under comparison; the terminal and central groups too match each other in the overall polarizability and the ratio of lateral to terminal attractions. On these counts the smectic-nematic thermal stabilities for both the series should have been the same. However, since the non-coplanarity of the molecules due to the bumping of oxygen atoms into the non-bonded sides of the adjacent hydrogens of the aromatic ring in the case of the present series and bumping of the hydrogen atom of the central azomethine group of the *n*-alkyl 4-*p*-acetoxybenzylideneaminocinnamate series⁷ differs; the non-coplanarity is less in the latter than the first. More non-coplanarity will decrease thermal stabilities; this is the case as far as the present ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates homologous series is concerned.

The smectic-nematic thermal stabilities for the corresponding odd and even homologues of both the series have been calculated; on comparison the difference of thermal stability between the odd and even homologues in both series is almost the same, i.e. 3.8 in the present series and 2.5 in the *n*-alkyl 4-*p*-acetoxybenzylideneaminocinnamates homologous series.

Thermal stabilities of the mesophases of this homologous series are compared with those of some similar homologous series studied earlier. Table 3 summarizes the thermal stabilities of the

TABLE 3—RELATIVE THERMAL STABILITIES

Average transition temperatures °C	Series			
	A	B	C	D
Smectic-Nematic or	119.0 (C ₂ -C ₁₂)	133.7 (C ₁₂ -C ₁₂)	152.5 (C ₇ -C ₁₂)	148.8 (C ₉ -C ₁₂)
Smectic-Isotropic Nematic-Isotropic	119.7 (C ₅ -C ₆)	138.25 (C ₅ -C ₆)	163.0 (C ₅ -C ₆)	203.0 (C ₁ -C ₄)
Commencement of smectic phase	C ₂	C ₄	C ₄	C ₇

series under comparison. The molecules of the homologous series A differ from those of the homologous series B in that they have 'benzene ring -CH₂-Me' ester in

A. Ethyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy) benzoates

B. Methyl *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates⁸

C. *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxycinnamoyloxy)propiophenones⁹

D. Biphenyl-4-*trans*-*p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamates⁸

place of 'benzene ring - Me' ester terminal group. Both smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic and nematic-isotropic thermal stabilities get sufficiently decreased with the addition of -CH₂ group. As the terminal ester substituent ring -CH₂-Me is replaced by ring -CH₂-CH₂-Me group¹⁰, both nematic and smectic thermal stabilities are further decreased. This progressive decrease in thermal stabilities of the mesophase has to be correlated with -CH₂ unit. The alkyl group is linked with the ester section through the O-linkage in case of the series A and B, the inductive effect due to additions of methylene, -CH₂, unit is rather less effective through O-linkage system than a direct linkage with C atom. Thus while increase in chain length increases polarizability thereby providing ground for enhancing thermal stability, the inductive effect as mentioned above results into weaker terminal attractions which cause progressive decrease in thermal stabilities with each methylene, -CH₂ unit added to the molecule.

The molecules of the homologous series C have the propionyl, -COC₂H₅ terminal group with ketonic bonding instead of the ester -COOCH₃ or -COOC₂H₅ terminal groups of the series B and A.

The thermal stabilities of the mesophases differ widely, those of the molecules with ring-ester groups being much lower. A comparison of the homologous series A and B with the homologous series D will show that while all other molecular features remain the same, the terminal ester $-\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$ or $-\text{COOCH}_3$ group is replaced by an aromatic ring in case of the molecules of the homologous series D. With a biphenyl ring, the overall polarizability increases besides a proportionate increase in the length of the molecules. Thus the thermal stabilities of the mesophases of the series D are very high as compared to those of the series A and B.

The early commencement of the smectic mesophase in the present series A can be attributed to the ester terminal groups; within the ester homologous series (A and B), the smectic mesophase commences earlier (at the second member) in case of series A than series B (at the fourth member) homologues which can be attributed to the increased chainlength of the series A molecules on account of additional $-\text{CH}_2$ unit which enhances overall polarizability of the molecules.

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